

The Influence of The Work Environment on Employee Performance at Bank Syariah Indonesia in The Medan Raya Area

Syahnant¹, Mesra B²

Magister Manajemen, Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*Email Correspondence: syahnantalghazali@gmail.com

Abstract

The aim of this research is to determine and analyze the influence of the work environment on employee performance at Bank Syariah Indonesia in the Medan Raya area. This research was conducted using a causal associative quantitative approach. The sample used was 100 employees from a total of 287 employees who were taken at random using random sampling techniques. The research results show that the work environment has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. This is shown by the T-value of $16.165 > t \text{ table } 1.66055$ with a P-Value of $0.000 < 0.05$. The regression coefficient shows that if the work environment is increased by 1 unit, employee performance will increase by 1,756 units assuming other variables remain constant. Apart from that, the results of the determination test show an Adjusted R Square value of 0.724 or 72.40%, which indicates that the work environment has a low influence on employee performance, while the remaining 27.60% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied. Thus, partially, the work environment has a positive and significant effect on the work of employees at Bank Syariah Indonesia in the Medan Raya area. This identifies that, meaning, improvements in the work environment can contribute to improving employee performance.

Keywords: Work environment; Employee Performance

INTRODUCTION

In the banking world, employee performance is an important factor that determines the success and continuity of a financial institution. This especially applies to Bank Syariah Indonesia in the Medan Raya area, where competition in the industry is increasing. Ensuring employee performance remains high is a must. However, to achieve maximum performance, serious attention must also be given to work environment factors and employee work motivation (Wijayanti & Heryanda, 2022).

A conducive work environment can have a significant influence on employee performance. A good work environment can create a supportive atmosphere, quality, and allow employees to develop professionally. On the other hand, work morale is also an important factor that can quality employees to work more productively and efficiently (Prakoso et al., 2014).

The work environment has an important role in achieving employee performance. This is because a pleasant work environment makes employees work more passionately and eagerly to achieve better performance (Irma & Yusuf, 2020).

It is hoped that this research can help banks improve the quality of work which will ultimately improve employee performance. By understanding how the work environment and work morale interact with employee performance, Bank Syariah Indonesia can take strategic steps to improve their performance. Furthermore, understanding the role of work quality as an intervening variable is also important to determine the extent to which the

influence of the work environment and work morale on employee performance can be mediated through work quality (Siagian, 2023).

The phenomenon that is occurring and is the main highlight and needs to be paid attention to by Bank Syariah Indonesia in the Medan Raya area is the increasing competition in the banking market, both from conventional and other sharia banking institutions. This competition requires Bank Syariah Indonesia to continue to improve its service quality and operational efficiency, which cannot be separated from employee performance (Ana & Zunaidi, 2022).

Behind these challenges, Bank Syariah Indonesia is also faced with internal problems related to employee performance. One of the main problems faced is inadequate employee performance, which can be caused by several factors, including a non-conducive work environment and a lack of work enthusiasm among employees. An unsupportive work environment can hinder employee quality and creativity, while low work morale can result in decreased productivity and work quality (Purba & Hutapea, 2022)

Based on the above phenomenon, there is a need for a deep understanding of how the work environment contributes to employee performance at Bank Syariah Indonesia in the Medan Raya area. Identification of these problems will help Bank Syariah Indonesia to take appropriate strategic steps to improve employee performance and answer the challenges of competition in the sharia banking market.

According to (Fahmi, 2017) Performance is the result of a process that is referred to and measured over a certain period of time based on previously established provisions or agreements. Meanwhile, according to (Mangkunegara. AA P, 2020) employee performance is the achievement of employee work results based on quality and quantity as work performance within a certain period of time which is adjusted to the duties and responsibilities of a group within the organization in carrying out basic tasks and functions that are guided by norms, standard operating procedures, criteria and measures that have been established or that apply within the organization.

To measure the level of employee performance in this research, the author refers to theory (Fahmi, 2017), namely: Quality, namely the level of errors, damage, accuracy. ; Quantity, namely the number of jobs produced; Use of time at work, namely the level of absenteeism, tardiness, effective working time/lost working hours and collaboration with other people at work.

Many factors can influence employee performance. This research is limited to work environment factors. According to (Sedarmayanti & Rahadian, 2018) the work environment is a situation where there are a number of groups in which there are several supporting facilities to achieve company goals in accordance with the company's vision and mission. Meanwhile, according to (Mangkunegara, 2016) the work environment is all the tools and materials encountered, the surrounding environment in which a person works, his work methods and work arrangements for individuals and groups.

The definition of the work environment in this research refers to the opinion of (Sedarmayanti, 2017), namely the non-physical work environment, namely all conditions

that occur related to work relationships, both relationships with superiors, relationships between co-workers, or relationships with subordinates.

To measure the work environment in this research, it refers to the indicators stated by (Sedarmayanti, 2017), namely the non-physical work environment as follows: Working relationships between subordinates and superiors and Working relationships between colleagues.

This research aims to analyze the influence of the work environment on employee performance at Bank Syariah Indonesia in the Medan area. The concept of this research is as depicted in the following conceptual framework image:

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

METHOD

This type of research is casual associative quantitative research with the aim of analyzing the pattern of relationships between variables with the aim of finding out the influence between two independent variables (exogenous) on the dependent variable (endogenous) (Kuncooro, Munajad, 2013). This research was carried out at Bank Syariah Indonesia in the Medan Raya area. This research was carried out from March to May 2024. According to (Sugiyono, 2018) population is a generalized area consisting of objects/subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics determined by the researcher to be studied and then conclusions drawn. The population in this study were all employees at Bank Syariah Indonesia in the Medan area, totaling 287 people with the following details:

Table 1. Total Population

Bank	Number of Employees
BSI Gajah Mada Branch	24
BSI Binjai Branch	22
BSI Binjai Branch Imam Bonjol	21
BSI Brandan Branch	21
BSI Stabat Branch	22
BSI Kabanjahe Branch	21
BSI Belawan Branch	24
BSI Gatot Subroto Branch	20
BSI Pancabudi Branch	14
BSI Tomang Elok Branch	19
BSI Ringroad Branch	20
BSI Setiabudi Branch	30
BSI Usu Branch	9
BSI Marelan Branch	20
Total	287

In this research the author used the Slovin formula to determine the sample size. The Slovin formula for determining samples is as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Information:

n = Sample size/number of respondents

N = Population size

e = 0.1

$$n = \frac{287}{1 + 287(0,1)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{287}{2,88}$$

n = 99.6 rounded to 100

Based on the calculations above, the sample of respondents in this study was adjusted to 100 people or around 34.8% of all employees at Bank Syariah Indonesia in the Medan area. This was done to make data processing easier and for better test results. The samples taken were based on probability sampling techniques; simple random sampling, where the researcher provides an equal opportunity for each member of the population to be selected as a random sample without paying attention to the strata in the population itself. The following are details of the number of samples taken.

Table 2. Number of samples

Bank	Total Population	Sample Percentage	Sample
BSI Gajah Mada Branch	24	34.8% x 24 = 8.35	8
BSI Binjai Branch	22	34.8% x 22 = 7.65	8
BSI Binjai Branch Imam Bonjol	21	34.8% x 21 = 7.30	7
BSI Brandan Branch	21	34.8% x 21 = 7.30	7
BSI Stabat Branch	22	34.8% x 22 = 7.65	8
BSI Kabanjahe Branch	21	34.8% x 21 = 7.30	7
BSI Belawan Branch	24	34.8% x 24 = 8.35	8
BSI Gatot Subroto Branch	20	34.8% x 20 = 6.96	7
BSI Pancabudi Branch	14	34.8% x 14 = 4.87	5
BSI Tomang Elok Branch	19	34.8% x 19 = 6.61	7
BSI Ringroad Branch	20	34.8% x 20 = 6.96	7
BSI Setiabudi Branch	30	34.8% x 30 = 10.44	10
BSI Usu Branch	9	34.8% x 9 = 3.13	4
BSI Marelan Branch	20	34.8% x 20 = 6.96	7
Total	287		100

The data that will be used from this research is the data from the questionnaire distributed to respondents consisting of all employees in all divisions. The data analysis

technique used in this research is a quantitative data analysis method using SPSS version 25.0.

Validity and reliability tests were carried out in order to test the quality of the research data. The validity test decision making criteria are as follows: If $r_{count} > r_{table}$, then the question item is valid. If $r_{count} < r_{table}$, then the question item is invalid. Meanwhile, the reliability test criteria are formulated if $r_{alpha} > r_{table}$ then the statement is reliable and if $r_{alpha} < r_{table}$ then the statement is not reliable.

The linear regression model was formulated in this research with the following formula:

$$Y = a + bX$$

Where :

Y = Employee Performance

X = Work Environment

a = Constant

b = Regression coefficient

The t-test in this research was carried out to determine the significance of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable (Kuncooro, Munajad, 2013). According to (Kuncooro, Munajad, 2013) the determination test (R^2) is used to measure how much influence the independent variable has on the dependent variable. In other words, the coefficient of determination is used to assess the magnitude of the influence of the independent variable studied, namely the work environment (X), on the dependent variable, namely employee performance (Y). The coefficient of determination (R^2) value ranges from zero to one ($0 < R^2 < 1$) which means, if $R^2 = 0$, then there is no influence between variable (X) and variable (Y). Conversely, if R^2 approaches 1, then the influence between variable (X) and variable (Y) becomes stronger. Testing of the coefficient of determination was carried out using SPSS version 25.0 software.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Contents Results and Discussion

1. Research result

a) Descriptive Analysis

Descriptive Analysis This test is used to determine the minimum and maximum scores, the highest score, the rating score and the standard deviation of each variable. The results are as follows:

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Work environment	100	3.00	5.00	4.3950	.45668
Employee Performance	100	3.30	5.00	4.3220	.46701
Valid N (listwise)	100				

The table above shows that the measurement results show that respondents assess the work environment and employee performance at Bank Syariah Indonesia in the Medan Raya area as above average, with mean values of 4.39 and 4.32 respectively on a scale of 1-5. The variation in respondents' assessments of these two variables is high, with almost the same standard deviation (0.456 for work environment and 0.467 for employee performance), indicating that although there are individual differences in perception, the majority of respondents have quite positive views of these two variables.

b) Validity and Reliability Test Results

Validity Test Results

The validity test is used to measure whether a questionnaire is valid or not. Validity testing carried out in this research was through the Corrected Item-Total Correlation test or better known as Person Correlation.

Table 3. Validity Test Results for Work Environment Variables (X)

Variable	Correlation Value	Probability	Information
X1	0.906 > 0.1966	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
X2	0.895 > 0.1966	0.000 < 0.050	Valid

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25

From the data above, it can be stated that the indicators for the gender variable have a correlation coefficient value of > 0.1966 with a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$ so it can be concluded that the indicators for the work environment variable are valid (Sugiyono, 2017).

Table 4. Validity Test Results for Employee Performance Variables (Y)

Variable	Correlation Value	Probability	Information
Y.1	0.893 > 0.1966	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
Y.2	0.901 > 0.1966	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
Y.3	0.839 > 0.1966	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
Y.4	0.875 > 0.1966	0.000 < 0.050	Valid

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25

From the data above it can be stated that all indicators on the employee performance variable have a correlation coefficient value greater than 0.1966 with a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$ so it can be concluded that the statements for the employee performance variable are valid (Sugiyono, 2016).

Reliability Test Results

According to (Ghozali, 2016) the reliability test aims to measure how reliable or reliable the questionnaire distributed to respondents is, which is useful as an instrument in this research. The reliability measurement method used in this research is by looking at the

Cronbach Alpha (a) value. The questionnaire is declared reliable if the Cronbach Alpha (a) value is > 0.61.

Table 5 Reliability Test Results

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
Work environment	0.766	2
Employee Performance	0.897	4

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25.0

Based on table 5, it is known that the Cronbach Alpha (a) value of the work environment and employee performance variables is greater than 0.60. So it can be concluded that all indicators in the variable instrument are declared reliable or reliable so that they can proceed to research hypothesis testing

c) Quantitative Analysis

This analysis is intended to determine the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable. The test results are as follows:

Simple Linear Regression Analysis

This regression test is intended to determine changes in the dependent variable if the independent variable experiences changes. The test results are as follows:

Table 6. Simple Linear Regression Test Results

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	1,803	,960			1,879	,063
	Work environment	1,756	,109	,853		16,165	,000

Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

Based on the test results in table 8, the regression equation $Y = 1.803 + 1.756X$ is obtained. This equation is explained as follows: 1) A constant of 1.803 means that if there is no work environment, then there is an employee performance of 1.803 points. The work environment regression coefficient is 1.756, meaning that the work environment influences an increase in employee performance by 1.756 for every 1 point increase.

Analysis of the Coefficient of Determination

To determine the magnitude of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable, a coefficient of determination analysis was carried out. The test results are as follows:

Table 7. Coefficient of Determination Test Results

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	RStd. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Change	Square Change	F Change	df1	df2
1	.853a	,727	,724	,98731	,727	261,300	1	98	,000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Work Environment

The test results in table 7 show that the Adjusted R Square value is 0.724 or 72.40%, which means that the work environment has a high influence on employee performance, while the remaining 27.60% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied.

t Test Results (Hypothesis Test)

Hypothesis testing with the t test is used to determine whether or not there is an influence of the dependent variable on the independent variable with the following hypothesis formulation:

Ho: There is no influence of the work environment on employee performance at Bank Syariah Indonesia in the Medan Raya area

Ha: There is an influence of the work environment on employee performance at Bank Syariah Indonesia in the Medan Raya area.

The following are the results of the hypothesis test as shown in the following table:

Table 8. Hypothesis Test Results

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	1,803	,960		1,879	,063
Work environment	1,756	,109	,853	16,165	,000

Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

Based on the test results in table 8, the calculated t value is 16.165 > t table 1.66055, with a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05, thus it can be stated that Ho is rejected and Ha is accepted or that there is a positive and significant influence between the work environment on employee performance at Bank Syariah Indonesia Medan Raya area.

Contents of Discussion Results

The findings in this research can be strengthened by referring to relevant previous research findings. These findings are supported by research results from (Tesmanto & Rina, 2022) and (Sarip & Mustangin, 2023) which state that the work environment has a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

The implication of these findings is that creating and maintaining a conducive work environment can increase employee productivity and overall performance. A positive work environment can include factors such as comfortable physical conditions, good interpersonal relationships, and adequate support and facilities from management. Thus, organizations that focus on improving the quality of the work environment will be more likely to achieve higher levels of performance from their employees. Apart from that, these findings also show the importance of management's attention to employee welfare as a strategy to increase the effectiveness and efficiency of organizational operations.

CLOSING

Conclusion

From the results of the research data analysis and discussion described above, it can be concluded that:

1. The results of the hypothesis test show that transformational leadership has a positive effect on employee performance. This can be seen from the T-count value of 16.165 > t table 1.66055 with a P-Value value of 0.000 < 0.05. This regression coefficient shows that if the work environment is increased by 1 unit, the change in employee performance as seen from the Y value will increase by 1,756 units assuming other variables are considered constant. Thus, partially the work environment has a positive and significant effect on employee job satisfaction at Bank Syariah Indonesia in the Medan Raya area.
2. Based on the results of the termination test, it shows that the Adjusted R Square value is 0.724 or 72.40%, which means that the work environment has a low influence on employee performance, while the remaining 27.60% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied.

Suggestions

Based on the results of the discussion and conclusions of this research, several things can be suggested to institutions, including:

1. Strengthen the implementation of the work environment to improve employee performance. Leaders must be more active in internalizing the organization's vision and values to all team members. This step can be done through leadership training that focuses on developing the ability to inspire and motivate employees, as well as ensuring that the organization's core values are understood and applied in daily activities. In addition, leaders need to continue to communicate organizational goals clearly and consistently to maintain focus and clear direction for employees.
2. Institutions must also facilitate open and two-way communication between leaders and employees. This can be realized through regular meetings, feedback sessions, and formal and informal mechanisms that allow employees to convey ideas, complaints, or suggestions. By creating a work environment that supports open dialogue, institutions can build trust and stronger relationships between leaders and employees, which in turn will improve performance and job satisfaction.
3. Additionally, it is important for institutions to consider individual needs and preferences in team management. The work environment must be adapted to the characteristics of each employee to maximize their potential. Institutions can conduct regular individual needs assessments and provide career development programs that suit employee aspirations. By paying attention to these individual aspects, institutions not only improve performance but also create a work environment that supports employee professional and personal growth, which ultimately will increase loyalty and productivity.

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